

METHODS AND AIDS OF PRESENTING TEACHING MATERIALS IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract: Teaching English is a dynamic process that requires careful planning and effective presentation of teaching materials. The way educators present these materials significantly impacts students' understanding, engagement, and overall language acquisition. In this article, we will explore some of the most effective methods and aids for presenting teaching materials in the context of teaching English as a second language.

Key words: Methods of teaching English, education, language techniques, learning, pedagogy, new devices, teaching materials.

Introduction

The role and influence of English today are gaining a higher speed in the world as well as in Uzbekistan. Currently, in the Republic of Uzbekistan great attention is given to the radical reorganization of the educational system that will give an opportunity to raise it to the level of modern standards. To facilitate successful English language instruction, various methods and aids can be employed to enhance the teaching and learning experience.

Methods of Presenting Teaching Materials

1. Communicative Language Teaching

CLT is an approach that emphasizes real-life communication and interaction as the primary goal of language learning. In this method, teaching materials are presented through authentic contexts, encouraging students to actively participate in conversations and activities that mirror real-world scenarios. CLT promotes meaningful language use and engages learners in tasks that require them to apply language skills in practical situations.

2.Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT)

TBLT focuses on assigning tasks that necessitate language use for completion. Teaching materials are presented in the form of tasks or projects, encouraging students to collaborate, problem-solve, and communicate effectively. TBLT helps learners develop not only linguistic skills but also critical thinking and creativity. This method provides a purposeful context for using the language, making the learning process more engaging and relevant.

3.Audio-Lingual Method

The Audio-Lingual Method utilizes audio recordings and repetitive drills to reinforce language patterns and structures. Teaching materials are presented through dialogues, recorded conversations, and language exercises. This method aims to develop students' listening and speaking skills by immersing them in the target language's sound patterns and intonation.

Aids for Presenting Teaching Materials

1. Visual Aids

Visual aids, such as slides, charts, diagrams, and videos, enhance comprehension by providing a visual representation of concepts. These aids are particularly useful for presenting vocabulary, grammar rules, and complex ideas. Visuals help make abstract concepts more concrete and memorable, catering to various learning styles within the classroom.

2. Interactive Whiteboards

Interactive whiteboards allow educators to display and manipulate teaching materials in real-time. They offer features like touch interactivity, multimedia integration, and internet access. Teachers can use these boards to write, draw, showcase videos, and engage students in interactive activities. Interactive whiteboards create an immersive learning environment that captures students' attention and encourages active participation.

3. Online Resources and Educational Apps

Incorporating online resources and educational apps into teaching materials presentation can significantly enhance the learning experience. These resources provide access to authentic language use, interactive exercises, and multimedia content. They also enable personalized learning, allowing students to practice at their own pace and receive instant feedback.

4. Multimedia Presentations

Multimedia presentations combine various media formats, such as text, images, audio, and video, to convey teaching materials. These presentations cater to different learning modalities and enhance comprehension. Educators can create dynamic lessons that appeal to visual, auditory, and kinesthetic learners, ensuring a more inclusive and effective teaching approach.

In conclusion, the methods and aids used to present teaching materials in English language instruction play a pivotal role in shaping students' language acquisition journey. Educators should select methods that align with their teaching philosophy and utilize aids that cater to diverse learning styles. By embracing innovative techniques and incorporating a variety of aids, educators can create engaging, interactive, and impactful English language lessons.

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